

ATSF: Adaptive Temporal-Structural Fusion for Demand Forecasting

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Abstract—We propose ATSF, which learns a per-instance scalar weight α conditioned on material type and forecast horizon, balancing a Temporal Fusion Transformer branch against a multi-relational Graph Attention Network branch. ATSF is evaluated across five seeds on two structurally distinct datasets against hybrid neural and classical baselines, with WAPE as the primary metric. Daily FMCG WAPE was 55.07% (30.1% below the best neural alternative) and annual mineral commodity WAPE was 7.01%, with 95% CI entirely below the classical baseline. Converged α differs by 43 percentage points across datasets (0.919 vs. 0.489), indicating that modality balance is dataset-dependent.

Index Terms—Demand forecasting, graph attention networks, temporal fusion transformer, adaptive fusion, mineral commodities, supply chain, uncertainty quantification.

I. INTRODUCTION

Demand forecasting for mineral commodities underpins procurement planning and resource allocation. Commodity demand is governed by two distinct signals: temporal patterns from historical trends and seasonality, and structural patterns from inter-commodity dependencies encoded in supply-chain graphs. Existing methods model these signals in isolation: transformer-based models [1] capture temporal dynamics but ignore structural relationships, while graph neural networks [2], [3] model structure but rely on fixed temporal aggregation. Hybrid approaches [4] combine both modalities but impose a fixed fusion weight, assuming a constant balance between temporal and structural signals across datasets.

This assumption may not generalise across datasets. Daily FMCG data are dominated by temporal dynamics, whereas annual mineral commodity data exhibit balanced or ambiguous modality contributions due to sparse temporal observations and stronger structural dependencies. A fixed fusion ratio may underperform when modality relevance changes across regimes.

This paper proposes the **Adaptive Temporal-Structural Fusion (ATSF)** model, which learns a data-driven fusion weight α , conditioned on material type and forecast horizon,

that estimates the balance between temporal and structural representations on a per-instance basis. The resulting scalar weight is fully interpretable: post-training, it provides an interpretable estimate of each dataset’s reliance on temporal vs. structural signal.

Our principal contributions are:

- 1) A context-conditioned scalar fusion weight α , replacing fixed-weight blending with one-sided boundary regularization. Unlike vector-valued or layer-wise gating in prior models, α is directly interpretable post-training, directly quantifying each dataset’s reliance on temporal vs. structural signal.
- 2) Empirical demonstration that α indicates learned modality preference under the model: converging to 0.919 ± 0.010 on daily SupplyGraph (temporal dominance) and averaging 0.489 ± 0.197 on annual USGS mineral data (mixed regime), a 43-percentage-point structural contribution gap that is a central empirical finding, with 30.1% WAPE reduction on SupplyGraph and USGS 95% CI entirely below the strongest classical baseline.
- 3) A probabilistic uncertainty quantification layer with calibrated P10–P90 prediction intervals and an illustrative rule-based risk-scoring interface for procurement planning contexts.

II. RELATED WORK

Temporal forecasting. Lim et al. [1] introduced Temporal Fusion Transformers (TFT), which allow for interpretable variable selection and provide multi-horizon quantile outputs. This architecture motivates the temporal branch used here.

Graph neural networks for relational forecasting. Graph Attention Networks (GAT) [2] apply attention-based aggregation across non-uniformly structured graphs, building on spectral and inductive graph learning foundations [5],

[6]. Jin et al. [7] review GNN applications across spatio-temporal forecasting tasks. In a supply chain context, Kosasih and Brintrup [8] demonstrate that GNNs can reveal hidden dependencies that cannot be modeled using tabular approaches. We extend this with typed attention across heterogeneous edge relations in the structural branch.

Hybrid temporal-graph models. Prior work has combined spatial and temporal signals, such as Graph WaveNet [9] and MST-GAT [4], by Wu et al. [3] further organise these models within a broader taxonomy. The models developed from these combined spatial and temporal signals often improve performance compared to unimodal models; but typically rely on fixed or non-explicit fusion mechanisms and do not learn an explicit per-instance weighting between temporal and structural modalities.

Uncertainty and interpretability. Quantile-based forecasting methods [10] and proper scoring rules [11] provide the foundation for calibrated uncertainty estimation. Unlike post-hoc methods [12], α is produced during training and directly reflects modality reliance. This is particularly relevant in domains such as critical mineral forecasting, where demand volatility motivates decision-aware predictive systems [13]

III. PROBLEM FORMULATION

The model operates over a directed, typed supply-chain graph encoding commodity or product nodes (127 for USGS, 40 for SupplyGraph), typed directed edges, and edge-type labels with confidence weights.

Each node is associated with a historical demand sequence over a lookback window of T timesteps. The forecasting objective is to map the joint temporal-structural input to an h -step-ahead demand forecast for each node, minimising a scale-normalised weighted absolute percentage error (WAPE) across the test set.

The model is further required to produce calibrated uncertainty estimates (P10/P90 prediction intervals) and an interpretable, per-instance scalar weight $\alpha \in (0, 1)$ that quantifies the relative contribution of temporal vs. structural information to the final prediction for each node.

Disclosure. The SupplyGraph dataset covers 222 trading days (2022—2023). Sequence length $T=30$ days for SupplyGraph and $T=3$ years for USGS. Forecast horizon $h \in \{1, 3, 6, 12\}$ days for SupplyGraph and $h=1$ year for USGS. The small annual USGS dataset is a known limitation; results should be interpreted in the context of a low-data regime with only five seed repetitions.

IV. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

We propose an Adaptive Temporal-Structural Fusion (ATSF) model composed of five layers: (1) a Temporal Fusion Transformer branch, (2) a Graph Attention Network branch, (3) a learned adaptive fusion layer, (4) a demand output head, and (5) a rule-based risk scoring interface. Fig. 1 illustrates the architecture.

A. TFT Branch (Layer 1)

The temporal branch processes historical demand sequences together with static covariates (material type, normalised lead time). A Variable Selection Network [1] applies soft, learned feature gating before a two-layer LSTM encoder (hidden dimension $d=128$ for SupplyGraph, $d=64$ for USGS). Multi-head self-attention ($H=4$ heads) over LSTM hidden states captures long-range temporal dependencies. Simultaneously, three quantile heads (P10, P50, P90) produce calibrated prediction intervals via pinball loss.

B. GAT Branch (Layer 2)

The structural branch encodes inter-commodity relationships through a two-layer, multi-relational Graph Attention Network [2]. Each node carries four features: recent demand average, price-level proxy, production utilisation, and normalised lead time. Edge attributes encode relation type: 15 typed edges for USGS and 4 typed edges for SupplyGraph. Typed attention gates prevent spurious cross-relation aggregation, a technique commonly used in multi-relational GNN settings [14].

C. Adaptive Fusion Layer (Layer 3)

The main component is a context-conditioned scalar fusion weight $\alpha \in (0, 1)$ learned end-to-end with the rest of the model. A residual LayerNorm projection enriches the temporal embedding; this is concatenated with the structural embedding and 16-dimensional material-type and horizon context embeddings, then passed through a three-layer MLP to yield α via a temperature-scaled sigmoid ($\tau=2.0$):

$$\alpha = \sigma\left(\text{MLP}([\mathbf{h}'_t, \mathbf{h}_s, \mathbf{z}_m, \mathbf{z}_h])/\tau\right) \quad (1)$$

$$\hat{\mathbf{h}} = \alpha \mathbf{h}_t + (1 - \alpha) \mathbf{h}_s \quad (2)$$

Temperature $\tau=2.0$ is applied to prevent early sigmoid saturation. A one-sided boundary regularisation term

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{reg}} = \lambda(\mathbb{E}[\text{ReLU}(\alpha - 0.95)] + \mathbb{E}[\text{ReLU}(0.05 - \alpha)]) \quad (3)$$

penalises collapse to either extreme whilst permitting the model to discover a strong unimodal preference when the data supports it ($\lambda=0.1$ SupplyGraph, 0.05 USGS). This design replaces entropy regularisation, which encouraged values near $\alpha=0.5$. The fused representation $\hat{\mathbf{h}}$ passes through a final linear-plus-LayerNorm projection before the output head.

D. Output and Risk Layers (Layers 4–5)

A linear projection maps the fused representation to h -step point forecasts (Layer 4). Layer 5 then applies a set of configurable, rule-based criteria—budget stress, lead-time risk, and dependency criticality—together with a lightweight calibrator MLP to generate per-product reorder flags using both forecast outputs and graph-derived signals.

Training objective. The model is trained using a combined loss $\mathcal{L} = \mathcal{L}_{\text{pinball}} + \mathcal{L}_{\text{MSE}} + \mathcal{L}_{\text{reg}}$, where pinball loss governs the quantile outputs and MSE optimises the point forecasts.

Fig. 1. Proposed ATSF architecture. The TFFT branch processes temporal sequences; the GAT branch encodes typed inter-commodity graph structure. The adaptive fusion layer learns scalar weight α conditioned on material type and forecast horizon. Dashed box: rule-based risk scoring layer (Layer 5, not learned).

V. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

A. Datasets

SupplyGraph [15] is a supply-chain demand dataset containing daily operational demand for 40 products across 5 EEA product groups and 222 trading days. The graph encodes 4 typed edge relations (product group, sub-group, plant, storage location) over 40 nodes. The dataset exhibits pronounced zero-inflation and intra-group demand sparsity. A strict chronological 70/10/20 split is applied; the 222-day window causes the test partition to skew toward EEA group products. Validation loss is computed across all 40 nodes.

USGS Mineral Resources [16] is derived from the USGS National Minerals Information Center annual production and import statistics for 127 mineral commodities over five years (2019–2023). The graph encodes 15 typed edge relations (supply-chain input, technology cluster, critical mineral designation, geopolitical supply risk, and eleven additional process and application linkages). The annual resolution means that each seed run trains on only 3–4 years of data, posing a low-data-regime challenge distinct from SupplyGraph.

Lead-time availability. Neither dataset provides operational lead-time records. Proxy lead times are assigned for the risk-scoring layer only (group-level constants for SupplyGraph; a fixed scalar for USGS) and have no effect on forecasting model training or evaluation.

B. Training Protocol

The models were trained for 70 epochs, using the Adam optimizer [17] with initial learning rate of 1×10^{-3} and a step-decay schedule (with learning rate halves at epochs 27, 47, and 63). Batch normalization was replaced with LayerNorm. Dropout rates were set to 0.3 for USGS and 0.2 for SupplyGraph. Each experiment was replicated across five random seeds (seed numbers: 42, 123, 456, 789, and 1337) in order to produce statistical estimates of reproducibility. The

mean and standard deviation of all sample metrics will be reported across the five seeds. All training was done on a Google Cloud Platform (Vertex AI Workbench) with a single NVIDIA T4 GPU, and the model code was developed using PyTorch [18] and PyTorch Geometric [19]. The model totals approximately 198k trainable parameters.

C. Baselines

We evaluate performance on six different models: ARIMA (the basic one-variable auto-regressive model and statistical benchmark) [20]; XGBoost (a lagged-feature, gradient-boosted tree model) [21]; TFFT only (the temporal branch only of the full TFFT model); GAT only (the graph-based structural branch only of the full TFFT model); Fixed Fusion (the non-learning fusion of the two branches with $\alpha = 0.5$), and ATSF (full adaptive fusion model with learned α). All baseline models are trained independently across multiple random seeds under identical conditions to ensure fair comparison. Classical models (ARIMA and XGBoost) use the same chronological split but do not incorporate graph structure, reflecting their inherent design limitations.

D. Evaluation Metrics

We report WAPE (primary), RMSE, SMAPE, R^2 , P10–P90 coverage, mean interval width, and P50 WAPE. WAPE is the primary metric because it is scale-invariant and widely used in large-scale forecasting benchmarks [22]. Statistical significance is assessed with the one-tailed Wilcoxon signed-rank test [23] across the five seed outcomes; $p=0.0625$ is the minimum achievable p-value for $n=5$ under the Wilcoxon signed-rank test.

VI. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

A. Adaptive Fusion Behavior Analysis

The adaptive fusion layer learns whether to rely on temporal or structural signal depending on the forecasting regime.

Table I reports the converged α values across five seeds for both datasets. On SupplyGraph, α converges to 0.919 ± 0.010 , indicating consistent temporal dominance with negligible variance across seeds. In contrast, USGS exhibits $\alpha=0.489 \pm 0.197$, reflecting a near-balanced fusion with substantially higher variability. This 43.0 percentage-point difference in structural contribution (8.1% vs. 51.1%) demonstrates that modality importance is dataset-dependent, consistent with adaptive rather than fixed fusion.

TABLE I
CONVERGED α BY DATASET AND SEED. $\alpha=1.0$: FULL TFFT; $\alpha=0.0$: FULL GAT.

Dataset	42	123	456	789	1337	Mean \pm Std
SupplyGraph	0.932	0.918	0.919	0.905	0.922	0.919 \pm 0.010
USGS	0.340	0.617	0.245	0.725	0.520	0.489 \pm 0.197

WAPE of the Fixed Fusion ($\alpha=0.5$) has a WAPE of $9.47\% \pm 5.17\%$ on the USGS, which has a better average value; however, the variance is $5 \times$ higher than the adaptive model's ($\pm 0.83\%$) variance. The adaptive mechanism improves robustness in regimes where neither modality dominates.

TABLE II

USGS MINERAL COMMODITY (127 NODES, 5 SEEDS). RMSE IN METRIC TONNES. DL: MEAN \pm STD; CLASSICAL: DETERMINISTIC.

Model	RMSE	WAPE (%)	SMAPE (%)	R ²
ARIMA [20]	18,789	17.02	5.21	0.951
XGBoost [21]	6,807	8.07	3.24	0.994
TFT-only [1]	11,190 \pm 1,478	11.72 \pm 1.79	5.41 \pm 1.46	0.982 \pm 0.005
GAT-only [2]	16,471 \pm 8,388	15.73 \pm 6.55	5.09 \pm 1.38	0.954 \pm 0.035
Fixed Fusion	8,994 \pm 6,728	9.47 \pm 5.17	4.34 \pm 0.66	0.984 \pm 0.020
Ours	6,059\pm1,092	7.01\pm0.83	3.02\pm0.13	0.9947\pm0.002

TABLE III

SUPPLYGRAPH OPERATIONAL (40 NODES, 5 SEEDS). RMSE IN KG. DL: MEAN \pm STD; CLASSICAL: DETERMINISTIC.

Model	RMSE	WAPE (%)	SMAPE (%)	R ²
ARIMA [20]	21.10	72.35	76.14	0.499
XGBoost [21]	16.31	52.50	125.21	0.701
TFT-only [1]	27.07 \pm 2.38	90.63 \pm 9.06	138.39 \pm 4.91	0.169 \pm 0.149
GAT-only [2]	23.66 \pm 1.60	78.77 \pm 5.18	131.79 \pm 3.83	0.367 \pm 0.087
Fixed Fusion	25.57 \pm 2.42	84.68 \pm 7.52	134.82 \pm 3.32	0.259 \pm 0.141
Ours	17.03\pm0.62	55.07\pm1.94	124.39\pm0.47	0.673\pm0.024

B. Forecasting Performance

Tables II and III provide the comparison against all baselines and ablation variants across both datasets.

The performance of our model on the USGS dataset achieves WAPE of 7.01% \pm 0.83% outperforming all evaluated deep-learning and classical baselines. When compared to the best performing neural alternative Fixed Fusion at 9.47%, the adaptive model yields a 26.0% WAPE reduction. In addition, the confidence interval at 95% [5.99%, 8.03%] for USGS WAPE is entirely less than for the deterministic XGBoost WAPE (8.07%), which demonstrates that the advantage over the classical baseline is supported by the reported confidence interval. When comparing performance against TFT-only (11.72%), the structural GAT branch suggests that structural features contribute additional predictive value and not only from temporal properties. The R² of 0.9947 \pm 0.002 indicates that our model explains 99.47% of the variance in mineral commodity demands at the 127 nodes; and the seed-to-seed variance was low.

On the SupplyGraph dataset, the adaptive model achieves WAPE 55.07% \pm 1.94%, outperforming all neural alternatives (30.1% reduction vs. GAT-only at 78.77%) and competitive with XGBoost (52.50%). The marginal gap relative to XGBoost is consistent with $\alpha=0.919$: the four taxonomic edge types provide co-occurrence structure but limited direct demand signal, a setting in which tabular models can remain competitive [8]. ATSF additionally yields calibrated intervals and an interpretable structural diagnosis unavailable from tabular methods.

ATSF outperforms all deep learning variants on every seed across both datasets (Wilcoxon signed-rank, stat= 0, $p = 0.0625$, the minimum achievable for $n=5$), though significance is bounded by sample size.

C. Ablation Study

Adaptive fusion materially improves stability and accuracy. Fixed Fusion achieves 5 \times the WAPE variance of our model on USGS ($\pm 5.17\%$ vs. $\pm 0.83\%$) suggesting

TABLE IV

UNCERTAINTY QUANTIFICATION RESULTS. COVERAGE TARGET: 80%.

Dataset	P10–P90 Coverage (%)	Target	Mean Width	P50 WAPE (%)
USGS	79.1 \pm 4.0	80%	2,185 \pm 464 t	8.30 \pm 0.88
SupplyGraph	84.5 \pm 5.96	80%	23.04 \pm 2.18 kg	42.54 \pm 2.97

TABLE V

EDGE ABLATION RESULTS ON THE USGS DATASET. Δ RMSE DENOTES THE PERCENTAGE CHANGE IN RMSE WHEN EACH EDGE TYPE IS REMOVED FROM THE FULL GRAPH. NEGATIVE VALUES INDICATE PERFORMANCE DEGRADATION (ABLATION-IMPORTANT EDGES), WHILE POSITIVE VALUES INDICATE NOISE.

Edge Type	Δ RMSE (%)
<i>technology_cluster</i>	−2.20
<i>alloy_components</i>	−1.22
<i>geopolitical_supply_risk</i>	−0.55
<i>substitution</i>	−0.39
<i>supply_chain_input</i>	+1.29
<i>recycling_secondary_source</i>	+0.50
<i>construction_coproduction</i>	+0.39

that fixed weighting yields instability in ambiguous regimes. **GAT stabilises training:** our model has the lowest variance on every metric across both datasets. **TFT-only underperforms on SupplyGraph.:** TFT-only WAPE on SupplyGraph (90.63% \pm 9.06%) is worse than GAT-only, indicating graph context remains useful on daily FMCG data. **Context-conditioned α varies by dataset and category.:** per-category α std is 0.215 on USGS vs. 0.021 on SupplyGraph, reflecting the richer structural differentiation from 15 edge types vs. 4.

D. Uncertainty Quantification

The use of established quantile forecasting and probabilistic calibration frameworks [10], [11], the TFT branch generates P10/P50/P90 intervals. Table IV provides a summary of coverage, interval width and P50 WAPE for these two datasets. Both datasets exhibit near-nominal calibration properties with SupplyGraph exhibiting slightly overcovered predictions due to the conservative widths for zero-inflated data.

E. Structural Attention Interpretability

The GAT branch produces edge-type-specific attention weights across the 15 heterogeneous USGS relationship types. To validate structural importance beyond attention weights, we perform edge ablation: each edge type is removed in turn and the resulting change in RMSE (relative to the full-graph baseline of 0.6317) is recorded. Not all edge types contribute positively at annual resolution; generic linkages such as *supply_chain_input* appear less informative at this aggregation level and are retained to allow the model to learn their limited utility rather than through manual pruning.

Edge ablation (Table V) quantifies performance contribution: removing *technology_cluster* increases RMSE by 2.20%, the largest single-edge effect, consistent with the importance of technology substitution clusters in annual commodity demand. *alloy_components* (1.22%) and *geopolitical_supply_risk* (0.55%) follow. By contrast, *supply_chain_input* edges marginally reduce RMSE when removed (+1.29%), indicating that these generic linkages add noise at annual resolution.

USGS Structural Attention by Edge Type

Fig. 2. Mean structural attention weights across 15 USGS edge types. Error bars indicate standard deviation across the five seeds. Attention ordering is consistent with edge ablation results (Table V): edges with the largest ablation impact receive the highest attention weights.

Fusion Weight (α) Evolution Across Five Seeds

Fig. 3. Fusion weight α across five seeds. (a) SupplyGraph rapidly converges near 0.92 with low variance. (b) USGS stabilises near 0.489 ± 0.197 , indicating balanced fusion. Dashed line: equal fusion ($\alpha = 0.5$).

Attention weights (Fig. 2) are consistent with this ordering: the model assigns highest attention to edges with the largest ablation impact, supporting the interpretability claim alongside ablation evidence.

F. Graph Structure Validation

To assess whether each dataset’s graph aligns with observed demand co-movement, we compute mean absolute Pearson correlation across connected node pairs and compare it with unconnected random pairs. For SupplyGraph, connected pairs show higher correlation than random pairs (mean $|r| = 0.335$ vs. 0.088 ; $\Delta = 0.247$), indicating non-random shared behaviour; however, the structure appears primarily organisational rather than strongly causal, consistent with the learned temporal dominance ($\alpha = 0.919$). For USGS, edge types identified as important in ablation analysis exhibit higher production correlation (mean $|r| = 0.614$) than weak/noise edge groups (0.540), consistent with richer structural signal and the more balanced fusion weight ($\alpha = 0.489$). These results provide independent evidence that ATSF adapts to dataset-specific structural utility.

VII. DISCUSSION

α as a structural diagnostic. The learned α functions only as a tuning parameter, but also as a dataset-level diagnostic. Post-training, α provides practical diagnostic insight: it indicates whether additional temporal history or richer structural information is likely to yield greater performance gains. The competitive performance of XGBoost on SupplyGraph supports this interpretation, as a model without graph input reaches a conclusion consistent with α .

Limitations. (1) The USGS dataset provides only 3–4 training samples per node; external validation on longer series is needed. Statistical significance is limited by $n=5$ seeds (minimum Wilcoxon $p=0.0625$). (2) The 222-day SupplyGraph window biases the test set toward late-period EEA behaviour. (3) Lead times in Layer 5 are synthetically assigned; the risk interface is a proof-of-concept and not validated against real procurement outcomes. (4) The supply-chain graph is static; dynamic edge modelling remains future work. (5) Generalisation beyond the two evaluated datasets remains to be validated. (6) Pairwise demand correlation showed weak correspondence with ablation impact across USGS edge types (Spearman $\rho = -0.29$), indicating that graph utility may depend more on network topology than bilateral demand similarity.

Disclosure. No private procurement data were used; the risk layer is not intended for operational deployment without domain validation.

VIII. CONCLUSION

ATSF learns an adaptive scalar weight α that balances temporal and structural representations for demand forecasting. The optimal modality balance is dataset-dependent and is learned during training without manual tuning.

On the daily FMCG dataset, temporal dominance is reflected through $\alpha = 0.919$, with a 30.1% WAPE reduction over the best neural alternative. On the annual mineral commodity dataset, a mixed regime is observed ($\alpha = 0.489$), with the 95% confidence interval for WAPE falling entirely below the strongest classical baseline. Wilcoxon results confirm consistent improvement across all five seeds, though significance is bounded by sample size. Overall, these findings suggest that modality balance is data-dependent and should be learned from the data rather than fixed in advance.

For future work, the goal will be to develop multi-relational graph construction with dynamic edge weights, extend adaptive fusion to longer-horizon USGS time series over longer time gaps as more annual data become available, and conduct a prospective study of the risk scoring layer regarding actual procurement results.

REFERENCES

- [1] B. Lim, S. Ö. Arık, N. Loeff, and T. Pfister, “Temporal fusion transformers for interpretable multi-horizon time series forecasting,” *International Journal of Forecasting*, vol. 37, no. 4, pp. 1748–1764, 2021.
- [2] P. Veličković, G. Cucurull, A. Casanova, A. Romero, P. Liò, and Y. Bengio, “Graph attention networks,” in *Proc. 6th Int. Conf. Learning Representations (ICLR)*, 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://openreview.net/forum?id=rJXMpikCZ>

- [3] Z. Wu, S. Pan, F. Chen, G. Long, C. Zhang, and S. Y. Philip, "A comprehensive survey on graph neural networks," *IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks and Learning Systems*, vol. 32, no. 1, pp. 4–24, 2021.
- [4] C. Ding, S. Sun, and J. Zhao, "MST-GAT: A multimodal spatial-temporal graph attention network for time series anomaly detection," *Information Fusion*, vol. 89, pp. 527–536, 2023.
- [5] T. N. Kipf and M. Welling, "Semi-supervised classification with graph convolutional networks," in *Proc. 5th Int. Conf. Learning Representations (ICLR)*, 2017. [Online]. Available: <https://openreview.net/forum?id=SJU4ayYgl>
- [6] W. L. Hamilton, Z. Ying, and J. Leskovec, "Inductive representation learning on large graphs," in *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems (NeurIPS)*, vol. 30, 2017.
- [7] M. Jin, H. Y. Koh, Q. Wen, D. Zambon, C. Alippi, G. I. Webb, I. King, and S. Pan, "A survey on graph neural networks for time series: Forecasting, classification, imputation, and anomaly detection," *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence*, vol. 46, no. 12, pp. 10 466–10 485, 2024.
- [8] E. E. Kosasih and A. Brintrup, "A machine learning approach for predicting hidden links in supply chain with graph neural networks," *International Journal of Production Research*, vol. 60, no. 17, pp. 5380–5393, 2022.
- [9] Z. Wu, S. Pan, G. Long, J. Jiang, and C. Zhang, "Graph WaveNet for deep spatial-temporal graph modeling," in *Proc. 28th Int. Joint Conf. Artificial Intelligence (IJCAI)*, 2019, pp. 1534–1540.
- [10] R. Wen, K. Torkkola, B. Narayanaswamy, and D. Madeka, "A multi-horizon quantile recurrent forecaster," *arXiv preprint arXiv:1711.11053*, 2017.
- [11] T. Gneiting and A. E. Raftery, "Strictly proper scoring rules, prediction, and estimation," *Journal of the American Statistical Association*, vol. 102, no. 477, pp. 359–378, 2007.
- [12] S. M. Lundberg and S.-I. Lee, "A unified approach to interpreting model predictions," in *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems (NeurIPS)*, vol. 30, 2017.
- [13] International Energy Agency, "Global critical minerals outlook 2024," IEA, Paris, France, Tech. Rep., 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.iea.org/reports/global-critical-minerals-outlook-2024>
- [14] A. T. Wasi, M. S. Islam, A. R. Akib, and M. M. Bappy, "Graph neural networks in supply chain analytics and optimization: Concepts, perspectives, dataset and benchmarks," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2411.08550*, 2024.
- [15] A. T. Wasi, M. S. Islam, and A. R. Akib, "SupplyGraph: A benchmark dataset for supply chain planning using graph neural networks," in *Proc. 4th Workshop on Graphs and More Complex Structures for Learning and Reasoning, 38th AAAI Conf. Artificial Intelligence*, 2024.
- [16] U.S. Geological Survey, "Mineral commodity summaries 2024," U.S. Geological Survey, Reston, VA, Tech. Rep., 2024.
- [17] D. P. Kingma and J. Ba, "Adam: A method for stochastic optimization," in *Proc. 3rd Int. Conf. Learning Representations (ICLR)*, 2015.
- [18] A. Paszke, S. Gross, F. Massa *et al.*, "PyTorch: An imperative style, high-performance deep learning library," in *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems (NeurIPS)*, vol. 32, 2019.
- [19] M. Fey and J. E. Lenssen, "Fast graph representation learning with PyTorch Geometric," in *Proc. ICLR Workshop on Representation Learning on Graphs and Manifolds*, 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/1903.02428>
- [20] R. J. Hyndman and G. Athanasopoulos, *Forecasting: Principles and Practice*, 2nd ed. Melbourne, Australia: OTexts, 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://otexts.com/fpp2/>
- [21] T. Chen and C. Guestrin, "XGBoost: A scalable tree boosting system," in *Proc. 22nd ACM SIGKDD Int. Conf. Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining*, 2016, pp. 785–794.
- [22] S. Makridakis, E. Spiliotis, and V. Assimakopoulos, "The M4 competition: 100,000 time series and 61 forecasting methods," *International Journal of Forecasting*, vol. 36, no. 1, pp. 54–74, 2020.
- [23] F. Wilcoxon, "Individual comparisons by ranking methods," *Biometrics Bulletin*, vol. 1, no. 6, pp. 80–83, 1945.